

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

VIEWS ABOUT GLOBAL ENGLISH AND DETERMINANTS OF ITS USAGE

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ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК И ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ ЕГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ

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Abstract

Global English embraces some factors that facilitate to its harmonic usage over the individual world countries. From this point, “lingua franca” has become a common communication device for the hundred millions of people. Nevertheless, recently there have also emerged some counteracting opinions on the extensive usage of English language by carriers of mother tongue. Such situation urges some language centers to more properly investigate the “factor analyses” of Global English determinants. The article makes some necessary theoretical and practical investigations to find out the major identifiers of Global English usage.

Аннотация

Глобальный английский включает в себя некоторые факторы, которые способствуют его гармоничному использованию в отдельных странах мира. С этой точки зрения, «lingua franca» стал наиболее общим средством общения сотен миллионов людей. Тем не менее, в последнее время появились и противоположные мнения о широком использовании английского языка носителями родного языка. Такая ситуация побуждает некоторые языковые центры более тщательно исследовать «факторный анализ» детерминантов Global English. В статье проводятся некоторые необходимые теоретические и практические исследования, чтобы выяснить основные детерминанты использования глобального английского языка.

Keywords: Global English, determining factors of a language use, ESP-EAP-EFB, history of ESL, language policy, contextual analysis of various purpose language usage

Ключевые слова: Глобальный английский, определяющие факторы использования языка, ESP-EAP-EFB, история ESL, языковая политика, контекстуальный анализ употребления языка в различных целях

Evidently language is considered a decisive or guiding factor in determination of national identity, formation of national culture, political will, national unity and some other national characteristics. However, the importance of national language does not eliminate the necessity of the second and sometimes the third language. That is, in the process of formation of each national language it may sometimes be needed to develop another, second language, for example English, along with the native tongue. In this regard, these days English is used by a number of nations as a global language as well as their mother tongue. It is rightly noted that "if we look through the statistics, we will see that despite the fact that English is the 3rd language after Chinese and Spanish in terms of its usage as a mother tongue, as it is considered a global language" [1, p.65]

There is no official definition for the "global" or "world" language, but anyway it essentially refers to a language learned and spoken internationally and which is characterized not only by the number of native and second language speakers, but also by its geographic location. Global English acts as a 'lingua franca', as a common language that allows people with different

backgrounds and ethnicities to communicate on a more or less equitable basis. However, are these the only conditions making this language global? Let us much closely approach the the essence of the matter. It is evident that, in any way, a personality's need for identity consists of the desire (conscious or unconscious) to use "own" language for communication purpose, which is acquired naturally in the first years of one's life. Such a language is habitually called as a mother tongue or a native language (the latter term may also have some other meanings). However, it is also a fact that "sameness" – monolingualism is considered the limiting case for satisfying such a need. Therefore, the concept of any language contact or the second language- bilingualism, is considered to be a socio- historical phenomenon that develops due to practical needs.

Since a language development is a dynamic process, it is not affected only by inevitable changes occurring within a language the language frame, a country or a group of languages, i.e. by intra linguistic changes, but also it gets affected by all the spectra of life and the course of general global economic and political trends. That is, along with the development of the mother

tongue itself, in the process of people's struggle for life and livelihood the conditions for triggering the usage of global language also get realized. It is the most universal means for self-expression of people. "A person who is a part of a certain society, who lives there or simply defines his/her existence, uses language, which is the most convenient tool to express his attitude to what is happening in society" [5, p.189]

However, which factors do become determining the dynamics of a language development? Do these factors always remain the same? It is inevitable that these conditions and factors can change since the formation and developmental dynamics of the language are unambiguously related to the situations conditioned by concrete socio-historical realities of a certain society. If in the past military factors were more effective in the expansion of the scale of the English language, these reasons can already be explained on rather a different level than these factors in the new development stage. In modern times, one of these reasons is that it is "taught as a second language more than other languages" [1, p.66]. Apparently, as a result of expansion the limits of global status of the English language, it has already become to strengthen its communicative, economic and technological capabilities. That is, "English has become a global language and more than 380 million people nowadays speak it as a first language and more than 200 million people take it as a second language, where another billion people are in the process of learning curve of this language" [2, p.1]. So, although English is mainly accepted as a means of communication in Western countries such as the United States, Canada or Great Britain, globalization, especially in the economic sector, has already turned English into a tool that facilitates to communication among people with different backgrounds and must.

The use of English is not the same in every country. "People in some countries (like the USA, Canada, England, etc.) grow up with it as their mother tongue, while others (like Ghana, Singapore, or India) benefit from this in addition to their mother tongue because English is used in their governments, laws, and it is important for the media and education system in their countries as a whole. And in the third group of countries (such as China, Germany, Russia or Spain), English is studied as the main foreign language in schools" [3, p.5]. For example, as a result of the rapid development of Azerbaijan in the recent years the widespread use of the English language, in turn, has also influenced the migration flow to this country. It is rightly noted that nowadays "Azerbaijan is also becoming a country of last destination for an increasing number of foreign citizens and stateless persons" [4, p.1].

Apparently, the factors in the cause-and-effect chain such as geographical, military-political, communicative advantages, migration of people to other countries for education that necessitate transformation of English into a global language start more and more rigorously serving as globalizing conditions for the prioritized usage of English in the educational sector which is now may also be counted as a major impactful force. Perhaps, English has already become the world's language of communication, as it is widely used in various

sectors; for example, in trade, technology, politics, and diplomacy. However, these spectra effect on this globalization process by different ways, where loss of cultural identity is considered one of the main resulting effects associated with globalization of English. At present, English as a global language has one form of influence on the language acquisition and cultural identity of people who adopt it as a second language in Africa and in the third world countries in Asia, and it has another form of impact in European countries.

Thanks to the harmonic language policy in Azerbaijan, the national language formation and some major related to this implementation processes in these directions have always been in the focus of attention by the government of Azerbaijan resulting in establishing the important economic, political and legal bases in the field of comprehensive usage of English language along with Azerbaijani. Because of thoughtful measures, Azerbaijan could preserve the harmonic development and coexistence of English, other languages and mother tongue. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated April 9, 2013 No. 2837 on the approval of the "State Program on the use of the Azerbaijani language in accordance with the requirements of time and the development of linguistics in the country" it is noted that "for foreign citizens learning the Azerbaijani language and those Azerbaijanis who want to learn a foreign language provisions by more intensive preparation of educational materials" should be considered as one of the important measures [6]. As a result of the conducted correct and targeted language policy, many empirical works and conceptual efforts aimed at the research of English and Azerbaijani languages during the last twenty or thirty years, English has been accepted as a "lingua franca" (ELF). That is, as a common language among speakers of different mother tongues where there is not any kind of suppression of the native language. Although the trend towards ELF (English as a Lingua Franca) has got strengthened, whether it is the phenomenon itself or research, its linguistic co-existence in communication has also harmoniously developed. However, with the expansion of the global language possibilities of the English language, there also have emerged some new trends in some parts of the world which is called as "anti-ELF" groups. These 'anti-ELF's' fall broadly into two camps: 1) those who dislike the ELF phenomenon as threatening 'standard' English (it is not clear what they mean by this vague term) and 2) those who see the growing tendency of ELF research paradigms. The first group includes mostly ELT (English Language Teaching) professionals, who propose a new monolithic type of English—a new global Standard English. Even today, in support to this some trends, web sites and blogs are proliferating in the expansion of the internet to identify key trends and take suggestions for the possibilities of British ELT. "Access to original materials and the potentials to use them to co-create content in English has recently been a real game changer which may be affected by their advice, but also by the surprise and confusion expressed from time to time" [7]. In this regard, issues such as teaching quality skills in the field of self-em-

ployment and learning meaningful work transition experiences for young people both inside and outside the South Caucasus the inequalities such as gender, class, disability and geographical origin have already become much widespread in research paradigms. Therefore, in order to study the factors that are potential to influence these statuses, the UK organizations, especially the Oxford University Language Centers have more rigorously started investigating the possible negative effects of the global English. For this purpose they are implementing some consistent and purposeful projects to contribute to the elimination process of these inequalities. Some scholars even argue that there are some conflicting interests between **the ethnic minorities' full participation in the dominant society and the preservation of their ethnic identity and ethnic group language**. However, it is also known that ethnic groups can fully participate in the dominant society and the individual mother tongues have the opportunity to preserve their heritage and language in a pluralistic society without assimilation for social mobility.

We believe that the study of English standards is taken for granted, but despite the global spread of English in any form, the very interpretation of ELF in two diametrically opposed ideological ways is a proof that both of these groups cannot be fully justified in their opinions to be right; and, actually, ELF researchers suggest that both of the above groups are wrong.

The role of ESP (English for Specific Purposes) is also important in the widespread use of English along with mother tongue. English for Specific Purposes is often treated as a purely pragmatic enterprise, a set of theoretical, methodologically grounded practice with only practical implications. No pedagogic practice is sufficient for learners to function independently beyond the language and learning, and hence ESP takes a clear theoretical stance on these issues with a long-term commitment to linguistic analysis, contextual relevance, and the pedagogical replication of community-specific communicative events.

Emerging in the 1970s with the development of a paradigmatic shift in the study of language for communication purposes, ESP used theoretical positions that offered the best advantages for practice and helped to further refine the field by analyzing the concerns that arose. That is why we can characterize ESP as a distinctive methodological approach that emphasizes a set of teaching patterns which recognize specific learner/student needs and the learner's subject matter expertise. Such definition provides an optimal environment for ESP to be taught for target groups to learn the language features, skills and genres, and this is considered a research base for the fields in terms of the need to define the different roles required by ESP practitioner in this endeavor. ESP practitioners try to take place in different cognitive, social and cultural contexts to exhibit literate activity, expand their language skills and demonstrate specific goals and understanding abilities in front of relevant field representatives with their activities. In this regard, ESP is closer to EAP (English for Academic Purposes) and EFB (English for Business) in terms of its teaching capabilities, but it is not the same

as them. We can see these differences from the contextual analysis of those fields and the way people refer to specific pragmatic contexts during their activities. At this point, ESP needs to be taken out of context as a display of social behavior and become important as discourse and literate practice. By other words, we can instill the term ESP in students by helping them discover how certain valued textual forms and practices are socially constructed in response to the common communicative purposes of certain social groups, referring to them as "socio-literate," and raising their scientific consciousness. That is, here the different aspects manifest themselves in three facets: 1. in specific social contexts; 2. in concrete forms and purposes and 3. in the relations between the roles of the participants. Since we are not talking about methods and forms of teaching English for different purposes and pedagogical methods, we keep these areas open for further and new researches.

The experience of the 90s played a special role in turning these fields into the special research subjects in the West. In this regard, Carol Huckin, Thomas N. Berkenkotter tried to clarify many interesting points in their research work entitled "Genre Knowledge in Disciplinary Communication Cognition/culture/power". Here, the authors outline the theory of genre knowledge from a socio-cognitive perspective and then elaborate on how it works through several case studies involving various forms of academic discourse, including scholarly journal articles, academic conventions, and post-graduate writing assignments. Through a grounded, largely inductive approach, they developed their theoretical framework consisting of the following five principles:

"Dynamism - genres are dynamic rhetorical forms that develop from actors' responses to recurring situations. Genres change over time in response to the socio-cognitive needs of the user; **Situation** - genres arise from the user's participation in communicative activities and are part of it; **Form and Content** - genre knowledge includes both form and content, including the sense of which content is appropriate and based on a specific purpose, situation and time; **Duality and Structure** – users both construct and reproduce social structures as they use genre rules; **Community Property** – genre conventions indicate the norms, epistemology, ideology and social ontology of the discourse community" [8].

Research has always played a strong role in teaching of ESP, and at this time, the scholars see the teacher not only as a consumer of this research, an analyst of the events and contexts in which the texts are used, but also as a user of these analysis and methods. It is based mainly on discourse analysis influenced by cross-cultural issues, social constructivism and Systemic Functional Linguistics. Based on pedagogical decisions of these sources and analysis, the teacher is constantly trying to interpret how some particular aspect of the real communicative world works and translate these concepts into practical classroom applications.

In the 90s of the last century, various different approaches to language choice and learning English as a second language began to develop further. In the early 1990s, a public body in the English education system

made a number of policy statements (for a selection see Macaro, 1997, 2001). These statements confirmed that, for all intents and purposes, English was the students' first language. This document says that "the foreign language (besides English) should be banned in the classroom and teachers should use only the target language" [9, p.35].

In the various surveys we have conducted some investigations on the role of the attitude towards the English language in our society, when we have witnessed the increasing interest in the English language

along with the Azerbaijani language. Thus, when analyzing the results of an oral survey conducted with 100 foreigners temporarily residing in the Republic of Azerbaijan and whose mother tongue is English. In terms of formation of identity, preservation of their mother tongue, and the study of intercultural relations, it was found that the interest in the Azerbaijani language is also of a great importance and as their mother tongue is for the national identity. (See: Table 1).

Table 1

"When learning a foreign language, the native language helps to maintain my identity" (results of an oral survey conducted with 100 foreign citizens temporarily residing in the Republic of Azerbaijan whose native language is English)

Completely disagree	8
Disagree	4
Agree	47
Completely agree	40
Hard to answer	1
Total	100

Finally, the survey has also covered the situation of with the language usage with the children. (See: Table 2) It became clear that the coexistence of mother tongue and foreign language does not create a great deal

of impediment in preservation of national identity. Moreover, in most cases the developed in harmony helping the kids to much easily integrate to the local or hosting community.

Table 2

Language used with children by national identity

Communicating to kids in English	More in Azeri than in English	More in English than in Azeri	Both lang-s equally	Total
English	9,5%	80 %	23,1%	18,3%
Both lang-s	35,7 %	20%	53,8%	38,3%
Only Azeri	54,8%	-	23,1%	43,3%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

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